

Effectiveness of Learning and Teaching Competency in Science Among Perspective Teachers

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Abstract:- Modern technology becomes a necessary tool for learning. This promotes arts and science in the field of education. The modern students prefer to use technology for effective learning. The sample of the study was done totally on 300; 150 male and 150 female of perspective teachers from different private B.Ed. colleges. The selection was done from 5 from urban and 5 from rural colleges respectively. The reliability of the teaching competency scale was calculated as 0.817.

Keywords:- Learning, Technology, Science, Teaching competency.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to 'Science Manpower Project', "Science is a cumulative and endless series of empirical observation which result in the formation of concepts & theories, with both concepts & theories being subject of modification in the light of further empirical observation. Science is both a body of knowledge & the process of acquiring & refining knowledge."

Science is organized and systematized learning. Science is a body of cumulative and ordered observations. Science is a process as well as the product.

Teachers have always played a pivotal role in the society. The future of the nation is being shaped in our classrooms; children are our future nation builders. Therefore, the teachers have a great responsibility in molding the character of children by giving quality education in the school. Teacher competency means the right way of conveying units of knowledge, application and skills to the learners. The right way of doing things is the competent way; the right way to perform a job, the right way to live and work in association and co-operation with others.

II. NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The whole education system spins in and around students' achievement in their education at the school level. The learning of students at schools level is depending upon different psychological, physical, economic, cultural, social factors and socio-economic status. Learning sciences becomes more important not only for the wellbeing of the individual but also for the society as a whole. Thus, learning achievement is a key element of the core curriculum of basic education. Teachers are

required to be innovative and they need to improve their professional knowledge and fulfill the expected competencies among students with special focus on science.

➤ Objective Of The Study

1. To find out level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender.
2. To find out level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality.
3. To find out the significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender.
4. To find out the significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality.

➤ Hypotheses Of The Study

1. The level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender is moderate level.
2. The level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality is moderate level.
3. There is no significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender.
4. There is no significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality.

➤ Sample of The Study

The present study adopted the normative survey method. 300 data were collected from B.Ed. students in 10 private colleges.

➤ Research Tool

Effectiveness of Learning and Teaching competency test developed and validated by the investigator.

III. ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

HYPOTHESIS - 1

1. The level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender is moderate level.

Table 1 Level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	120	24
Moderate	215	43
High	165	33

Fig 1Figure shows frequency of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender

2. The level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality is moderate level.

Table 1.2 Level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	70	35
Moderate	240	48
High	90	18

Fig 2 Figure shows frequency of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality

3. There is no significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender.

Table 3 Mean, Standard deviation and C.R value of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	C.R.	Remarks
Effectiveness of Learning and Teaching competency in Science	Male	150	73.74	9.29	0.782	1.38	NS
	Female	150	74.01	9.75	0.773		

From the above Table the calculated (CR) value (1.38) is found to be less than the table value (1.96). Hence there is no significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender. Therefore the above hypothesis is accepted.

4. There is no significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality.

Table 4 Mean, Standard deviation and C.R value of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality

Variable	Locality	N	Mean	S.D.	SEM	C.R.	Remarks
Effectiveness of Learning and Teaching competency in Science	Rural	195	74.70	9.174	0.725	0.48	NS
	Urban	105	76.16	7.673	0.756		

From the above Table the calculated (CR) value (0.48) is found to be less than the table value (1.96). Hence there is no significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Locality. Therefore the above hypothesis is accepted.

IV. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. The level of effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender and Locality is moderate level.
2. There is no significant difference in effectiveness of learning and teaching competency in science of perspective teachers with reference to Gender and Locality.

V. CONCLUSION

This study implies that teachers and parents should pay special attention to encourage and motivate students to develop a good study habit and increase the absorption of information received from learning. Consequently, it will improve their teaching competency in science.

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